

Project Website

Due date: 30/04/2024

Responsible partner: Enspire
Science Ltd.

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Document information

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D7.1							
DELIVERABLE NAME	Project Website							
ANNEXES	-							
TYPE*	R:		DMP:		DATA:		DEC:	X
DISSEMINATION LEVEL**	PU:	X	SEN:		EU CLASSIFIED:			
LEAD BENEFICIARY	Enspire Science Ltd.							
DUE DATE	30.4.2024							
SUBMISSION DATE	30.4.2024							

*R — Document, report; DMP — Data Management Plan; DATA — data sets, microdata, etc; DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.

**Public — fully open (automatically posted online); Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; EU classified — restraint-ue/eu-restricted, confidentiel-ue/eu-confidential, secret-ue/eu-secret under decision 2015/444

Document history

ID	DATE	AUTHOR	CHANGE
1.	21.4.2024	Lara-Cristina Amăriuți, Enspire	First draft
2.	28.4.2024	Lara-Cristina Amăriuți	Final version
3.	13.07.2025	Lara-Cristina Amăriuți, Enspire	This version includes changes made to the website after the initial submission of this deliverable, as well as changes made following the project's first periodic review: 1. The "The Project" top bar menu got replaced with a drop-down menu called "About" 2. The homepage features two maps

			<p>set in Juba, South Sudan, and Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of Congo to emphasize the project locations.</p> <p>3. A “Work Packages” page has been added to showcase the structure of the project’s work packages, linking consortium partners to their respective work.</p> <p>4. Consortium member organisational bios have been updated to reflect any relevant experience working with the humanitarian sector; Humanitarian consortium members’ organisational bios have been updated to reflect their experience working in the project’s 2 selected locations.</p> <p>5. The “Resources” page now features a “Publications and presentations” section where all public presentations and event materials will be stored.</p>
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Introduction

This deliverable (D7.1) showcases a general overview of the **Bio4HUMAN** project website, its contents, and functionality. The **Bio4HUMAN** website can be accessed at the following link: <https://bio4human.eu/>. The website is scheduled to launch on April 30, 2024, and is expected to attract 8,000 visitors, 3,000 active users, 25,000 event counts, 5,000 sessions, and 10,000 views over the project’s lifecycle. The website is designed to cater to all of **Bio4HUMAN’s** target audiences.

To ensure that the project website remains relevant to our audience, three surveys are sent out to website visitors (SurveyMonkey, Qualaroo) in M10, M20, and M30 of the project, with an expected total of 50 responses for the duration of the project. The survey is meant to collect user experience information from Bio4HUMAN website visitors. More comprehensive data on the first user experience survey can be seen in Annex 1 of the document.

D7.1 is a living deliverable in that the version of the website published on 30 April 2024 is just the start, and the website will be continuously updated as the project progresses.

The Bio4HUMAN website

The Bio4HUMAN website contains the following sections and subsections as listed below.

- **Homepage** – the homepage contains a general overview of the project and sections outlining its vision, project locations, partners, and highlights.
- **About** – a dropdown menu on the top header of the website containing the following pages:

- **About Bio4HUMAN** – the project page contains an in-depth description of the project and its objectives, a link to the project’s factsheet on the European Commission’s CORDIS website, a link to a subsection of the **Bio4HUMAN** website outlining the project’s work packages and their associated beneficiaries, and lastly a section containing general information about the project such as duration and budget.
- **Work Packages** – the work packages page contains the project’s work package structure and mentions the responsible partners for each work package.
- **About Our Sister Project** – this page is dedicated to **Bio4HUMAN’s** sister project, Waste in Humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation (WORM). The page contains brief information on WORM as well as a link to the project’s website.
- **Expected Results, Outcomes and Impacts** – this page contains information on **Bio4HUMAN’s** short-term expected results, medium-term expected outcomes, and long-term expected impacts.
- **Consortium** – the consortium page features all ten partners involved in the **Bio4HUMAN** project and a detailed description of each. Where possible, relevant experience in working with the humanitarian sector has been added to these descriptions. The Humanitarian partners within the **Bio4HUMAN** consortium have also outlined their experiences operating in the project’s two locations, South Sudan and the Democratic Republic of Congo.
- **News and Events** – the news and events page features all the project’s press releases, publications, and articles that will be posted. This page will also feature a discussion forum meant to engage the project’s target audiences.
- **Resources** – the resources page features the project’s public deliverables, communications materials (such as leaflets and two-pagers), thematic webinar recordings, and publications and presentations.
- **Clustering** – the clustering page showcases **Bio4HUMAN’s** collaborations with other relevant projects and networks.
- **Contact** – the contact page contains a contact form that visitors can use to contact **Bio4HUMAN’s** project coordinators.

Below are some images featuring some of the different pages on the website.

Figure 1: Website Homepage

Figure 2: Website Project page

Consortium

Enspire science **Enspire Science**

Enspire Science Ltd. is a leading project management, consulting, and training service provider in the field of EU-funded projects, with unique expertise in the ERC Funding scheme, supporting thousands of ERC applicants to date in the full spectrum of the scientific community. The company also has extensive experience in running and coordinating EU-funded projects for over 2 decades by now. As project coordinator, Enspire Science will lead the Project Management work package (WP1), and the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation work packages (WP7&8).

RESEARCH CENTER **ITENE**

ITENE has been offering tailor-made ready-to-market solutions for over 30 years to all the companies that make up the value chain in the 4 main areas in which they support, namely, materials and technologies for the circular economy, safety, design and functionality of packaging, safety and environmental monitoring technologies, and transport, mobility and digital transformation.

To this end, ITENE has the expert knowledge and infrastructures that allow them to cover everything from technology development to validation in industrial environments.

Figure 3: Website Consortium page

The screenshot shows the 'News and Events' section of the website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the BIO4HUMAN logo and links for 'About', 'Bio4HUMAN Consortium', 'News and Events', 'Resources', 'Clustering', and 'Contact Us'. Below the navigation bar is a green header with the text 'News and Events'. The main content area features several news items:

- Discussion Forum / News and Events: Evaluating bio-based materials' impact in aid** (July 31, 2023). This item includes a graphic with four questions:
 - How can we fairly compare bio-based and fossil-based materials using life cycle assessment (LCA)?
 - Which environmental indicators (e.g. GHG emissions, land use) are most relevant for evaluating the environmental impact of bio-based materials (e.g. bioplastics, bio-based packaging, water usage) compared to fossil-based materials?
 - Have you ever had to choose between different materials for a product where environmental impact was a key factor? Which indicators were most important in your decision?
 - Do you think certain environmental indicators are under-represented in standard LCAs (e.g. land use, plastic waste, end-of-life challenges)?
- Discussion Forum / News and Events: Your input counts – bio-based and humanitarian actors, share your thoughts!** (July 31, 2023).
- News and Events: Bio4HUMAN: 15 Months of Progress Toward Sustainable Humanitarian Solutions** (June 24, 2023). The text states: "Our second project video is here! From biodegradable hygiene products to micro-biogas digesters, Bio4HUMAN identified B1 promising bio-based innovations for humanitarian settings. In this video, discover how our team assessed..."
- News and Events / Press Releases: Bio4HUMAN's Third Project Consortium Meeting**.

Figure 4: Website News and Events page

Figure 5: Website Resources page

Figure 6: Clustering page

Contact Us

You can contact us by filling in the form below or sending an email to inquiry@bio4human.eu

Your name *

Your email *

Subject

Your message *

SUBMIT

Figure 7: Website Contact page

Annex 1 – First website survey report

Introduction

This report is meant to showcase the results obtained as part of our first website survey. The website survey was meant to collect user experience information from Bio4HUMAN website visitors.

The survey

The first website feedback survey contained the following questions:

1. Is this the first time you've visited our website?
2. What is your most likely reason for visiting our website?
3. Did you find all the information you were looking for?
4. How easy is it to find the information you are looking for on our website?
5. How likely are you to recommend this website to your peers?
6. What can we do to further improve your experience on our website?

The questions offered multiple-choice answers that users could choose such as “Yes”, “No”, and “Some of it”, “Very likely”, “Likely” and “Not likely”.

Question 3 of the survey offered 3 predefined answers:

- To learn more about the project.
- To find and download project deliverables.
- Other (please specify below)

Question 4 offered a scale of answers ranging from “Very Easy”, to “Average” to “Very Difficult”.

Question 6 was an open-answer question, and enabled users to freely add their suggestions.

Figure 8: Bio4HUMAN - First web feedback survey

Results

The survey was shared via the Bio4HUMAN website, as well as on the project's social media platforms. The form was filled out by 12 respondents. The valuable input collected by this survey will be used to further improve the Bio4HUMAN website usability. The graphs below outline the responses received by all respondents per question.

Figure 9: First survey question answer distribution

The first question of the survey asks respondents if this is their first time visiting the Bio4HUMAN website. Of the 12 total respondents, 4 answered “No” and 8 answered “Yes”.

Figure 10: Second survey question answer distribution

The second question of the survey asks respondents what their reason is for visiting the project website. All 12 respondents answered with “To learn more about the project.”

Figure 11: Third survey question answer distribution

The third question of the survey asks respondents if they found all the information they were looking for on the website. Of the 12 total respondents, 4 answered “No” and 8 answered “Yes”.

Figure 12: Fourth survey question answer distribution

The fourth question of the survey asks respondents how easy it is to find the information they are looking for on the website. Of the total 12 respondents, 2 answered “Very easy”, 8 answered “Easy” and 2 answered “Average”.

Figure 13: Fifth survey question answer distribution

The fifth question of the survey asks respondents how likely they are to recommend Bio4HUMAN’s website to their peers. Of the total 12 respondents, 5 answered “Very likely” and 7 answered “Likely”.

The final question of the survey was an open-ended question: *What can we do to further improve your experience on our website?* For this question, we received the following input:

- *I love your website! Perhaps I would put news on the Home Page.*
- *I think the user experience could be enhanced by presenting some key deliverables or tangible outcomes directly on the homepage. This would make the project more concrete and accessible for first-time visitors, helping them immediately grasp its purpose and impact.*
- *Do not underline text if there is no hyperlink, it confuses the user that the text leads to some other resources/website. I would add to the front page a couple of solutions you offer very high level -for people that have very limited knowledge about the topic it would be useful to understand what is your project about.*
- *The UX is not the best, the buttons and banners are not that good - almost missed it all. The menu section "The project" has one down menu and by itself is clickable, which I didn't expect and almost missed reading "About Us" info. The pictures are not the best used -it makes the website looks fake... If I didn't know that it's real, I would not have a good feeling about it. I also miss photo-gallery of how things go with all the projects - it would also make it more reliable that things go well. And there is no section with people, who works on there projects and responsible people for it and their "about", so I would know who I will work with - you have great people in this, its pity to not have them "shine" :). Over all really good, it just needs a good UX designer.*
- *It would be nice to make the website more user friendly, especially from accessibility standpoint.*
- *Everything looks good!*